

Table S2 Summary of previous geochronological data of the Almalyk district.

Magmatic-hydrothermal evolution	Sample description	Sample location	Dating method	Age \pm deviation (Ma)	Reference
Late Silurian–Early Devonian island arc magmatism	Granosyenite porphyry	Kalmakyr	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	422 \pm 4 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Dolgoplova et al. (2017)
	Monzonite	Kyzata	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	416 \pm 9 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Seltmann et al. (2011)
Early Carboniferous continental arc magmatism	Granodiorite porphyry	Sarycheku	LA–ICP–MS zircon U–Pb	337.8 \pm 3.1 ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Cheng et al. (2018a)
	Gabbro	Kalmakyr	LA–ICP–MS zircon U–Pb	335.0 \pm 2.4 ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Cheng et al. (2018b)
	Monzonite	Kalmakyr	LA–ICP–MS zircon U–Pb	327.2 \pm 5.6 ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Zhao et al. (2017)
	Quartz monzonite	Kalmakyr	LA–ICP–MS zircon U–Pb	326.1 \pm 3.4 ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Cheng et al. (2018a)
Late Carboniferous continental arc magmatism	Deformed granite	Kara-Kiya	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	317 \pm 8 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Seltmann et al. (2011)
	Granodiorite porphyry	Kalmakyr	LA–ICP–MS zircon U–Pb	315.2 \pm 2.8 ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Cheng et al. (2018a)
	Altered quartz syenite	Kalmakyr	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	315 \pm 2 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Dolgoplova et al. (2017)
	Granodiorite porphyry	Kalmakyr	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	315 \pm 1 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Seltmann et al. (2011)
	Granodiorite porphyry	Kalmakyr	LA–ICP–MS zircon U–Pb	313.6 \pm 2.8 ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Zhao et al. (2017)
	Monzonite dike	Sarycheku	LA–ICP–MS zircon U–Pb	313.2 \pm 2.5 ($\pm 1\sigma$)	Cheng et al. (2018a)
	Andesite-dacite	Sarycheku	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	311 \pm 3 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Dolgoplova et al. (2017)
	Altered monzonite	Kalmakyr	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	308 \pm 4 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Seltmann et al. (2011)
	Monzonite	Kalmakyr	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	308 \pm 1 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Seltmann et al. (2011)
	Granodiorite porphyry	Sarycheku	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	306 \pm 3 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Seltmann et al. (2011)
Late Carboniferous porphyry Cu–Au mineralization	Early stage of quartz-molybdenite veins	Kalmakyr	Molybdenite Re–Os	(313.2 \pm 7.2) ~ (312.2 \pm 4.7) ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Zhao et al. (2017)
	Main stage of quartz-sulfide veins	Kalmakyr	Molybdenite Re–Os	(310.4 \pm 5.2) ~ (306.3 \pm 4.3) ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Zhao et al. (2017)
Early Permian post-collisional A-type magmatism	Granite	Sarycheku	SHRIMP zircon U–Pb	297 \pm 3 ($\pm 2\sigma$)	Seltmann et al. (2011)
Poorly-constrained, low-precision data	Diorite	Kalmakyr	K–Ar	330–321	Cai and Li (1995a)
	Quartz monzodiorite	Kalmakyr	K–Ar	319	Cai and Li (1995a)
	Granodiorite porphyry	Kalmakyr	K–Ar	311–292	Cai and Li (1995a)
	Phyllic altered rocks	Kalmakyr	?	309	Cai and Li (1995b)
	Phyllic altered rocks	Sarycheku	?	315	Cai and Li (1995b)
	Granodiorite porphyry	Sarycheku	?	339	Cai and Li (1995b)
	Propylitic altered rocks	Dalnee	?	305	Cai and Li (1995b)
	Altered rocks	Kalmakyr	Bulk K–Ar	320–280	Golovanov et al. (2005)
	Mica in quartz-sulfide vein	Kalmakyr	White mica K–Ar	304	Golovanov et al. (2005)
	Sericite in altered rocks	Kalmakyr	Sericite K–Ar	303–301	Golovanov et al. (2005)
	Phlogopite in altered rocks	Kalmakyr	Phlogopite K–Ar	294	Golovanov et al. (2005)
	Hydromica in altered rocks	Kalmakyr	Hydromica K–Ar	276–273	Golovanov et al. (2005)

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